

ERGONOMIC PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS THROUGH DIGITALIZATION OF MODERN EDUCATION.

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Annotation. The main goals of ergonomics are to facilitate the employee's adaptation to natural, social, psychological and technical organizational conditions in production. The focus of ergonomics is to find ways and methods of adapting human activity and production environment to the characteristics and capabilities of the human body in specific production conditions. Based on its research, ergonomics develops recommendations for improving working conditions and reorganizing the work process.

Key words: ergonomics, employee working in ergonomics, professional activity, ergonomic educational environment.

Archaeological finds of tools used in the early stages of the development of society show that all changes made by man to objects of natural origin were related to their ease of use and functional purpose in accordance with human needs.

Ergonomics studies the functional characteristics of workers, the law, methods and methods of work processes to create optimal conditions, specific measures to ensure effective, mental and physical development of people in workplaces, comfortable and safety for workers, and maintaining their health. performs his work[1,2].

Today, at a time when it is difficult to imagine technological processes, computer tools, production without various machines, organizing the work of employees in the field of education, maintaining regulatory documents, further improving the working conditions of workers, ensuring human safety, in the first issue It is important to preserve human health, and economically, to preserve the working ability of employees. The science of ergonomics deals with these issues, that is, this is its main task [3,4].

The main principles of the state policy in the field of education are to provide education based on state educational standards, state educational requirements and curricula, to develop the young generation in all respects based on a specific goal and socio-historical experience. In a systematic process aimed at developing the mind, behavior and outlook of students, organized on the basis of a specific project, aimed at achieving a specific goal, organizing a pedagogical process that guarantees the educational result, knowledge of pedagogical ergonomics from teachers of higher education, requires ergonomic culture based on skills and competencies[5,6].

Conducting lessons remotely using the Internet and information and communication technologies, organizing them on the basis of a specific project, using the most effective methods in pedagogical processes aimed at achieving a specific goal, guaranteeing the educational result, choosing educational and educational technologies and ergonomic culture ensures the effectiveness of organization of lesson processes[7].

Modernization of the educational system, its structural reconstruction, changing and updating the educational programs taking into account the modern achievements of education, science, technology and technology, economy and culture at the world level envisages today[8].

Wide adoption of advanced technologies, positive changes in the economy, expansion of the scope of foreign investments, development of entrepreneurship, small and private business, as well as integration of continuous education with science and production, abilities of learners and The introduction of a differentiated approach to education in accordance with its capabilities is the basis for improving the advanced pedagogical technologies of education, the creation of modern educational and methodological complexes, the system of organizing and managing pedagogical processes in accordance with the requirements of pedagogical ergonomics[9,10].

This, in turn, is the responsibility of the managers and pedagogues of advanced educational institutions to implement world-class achievements of education, science, technology and technology, science-based innovations to improve the ergonomic culture of

managers and pedagogues of general secondary educational institutions. organization and management of pedagogical processes based on the requirements of pedagogical ergonomics, as well as new tasks in the direction of ensuring the effectiveness of pedagogical processes[11,12].

The material and technical base of each science office, the use of technical means and equipment of education, the organization of training and learning processes of teachers and students based on safe and convenient pedagogical and ergonomic requirements, professional activity from the teacher, requires integrative activity and ergonomic culture[13,14].

Professional activity is expressed in the regulatory and legal documents of education, management skills, the basics of pedagogical ergonomics, the office system, the introduction of information and communication technologies in the educational process and management, professional competence, knowledge of foreign languages.

The level of professional activity - the level of professional qualification, work experience in relevant functional tasks, compliance with the professional field, knowledge of functional tasks in the position held, initiative, level of creative approach to work, objectivity, transparency, levels of personal and professional competence, practical experience , the availability of management skills, knowledge of special pedagogical ergonomic requirements for educational tools and material technical base, professional culture, responsible, position in the team and a number of similar qualities are determined. Professional competence, ergonomic culture, initiative, personal pedagogical qualities, skills and experience of managing students' learning processes, systematic analysis and decision-making skills, optimal and effective ways of performing duties, first of all, based on the requirements of state policy The presence of implementation skills in leaders and pedagogues has a positive effect on the effectiveness of the educational institution[15,16].

This, in turn, creates opportunities for expanding the scope of professional interests of professors and teachers, that is, for them to conduct theoretical psychological-pedagogical and fundamental research from reading literature. "Pedagogical ergonomics" is one of the

areas that ensure the effectiveness of scientific-pedagogical training, professional activity and innovative activity in this regard. Professors and teachers who actively participate in innovative processes regularly develop themselves professionally and become catalysts for improving the educational system, that is, they play an important role in the acceleration of these processes[17,18].

Ergonomic culture is a generalized activity, which is based on the systematic planning of the internal activities of the educational institution aimed at achieving positive results in the activities of educational staff, developing pedagogical processes, and adapting teachers and students to their workplaces. it is necessary to ensure and implement the safety and convenience of the educational process[19,20].

Research hypothesis: in the case of pedagogical ergonomics, objective and subjective factors cause the improvement of ergonomic culture of teachers in an educational institution. Objective factors include the state's new educational policy, fundamental and applied research in the field of education, and the educational institution's experiences in innovative activities.

Subjective factors include socio-territorial needs, the development process of the educational activity of the educational institution, the need for ergonomic knowledge, skills and qualifications of pedagogues, the development of scientific potential, the growth of the potential of the educational institution, the educational process an example is a change in organizational and management characteristics[21].

Modern socio-economic reforms that are being implemented now have a direct impact on the education system. Modernization of education implies its democratization, socialization and humanization, ensuring the safety and convenience of the educational process based on the adaptation of teachers and students to the workplace, and strengthening the integration processes, improving the connection between education and production. . These processes, in connection with the objective changes of socio-cultural situations, as one of the main factors influencing the improvement and development of pedagogical

processes, the need for qualified specialists who have mastered the requirements of pedagogical ergonomics and developed ergonomic culture defines[22,23].

Taking into account the characteristics of the influence of objective and subjective influencing factors affecting the improvement of the ergonomic culture of the listeners, we determined the criteria and indicators for evaluating the level of formation of the ergonomic culture of the listeners (high, medium, low)[24]:

- a) the cognitive feature describes the knowledge of the listeners about the ergonomic culture and the ways of its formation;
- b) determines the attitude to the problems of forming the ergonomic culture of motivated listeners;
- c) integrative activity shows the acquisition of ergonomic abilities and skills to create a comfortable, effective and safe learning environment in modern education.

Thus, in the regional centers of retraining of higher education employees and their qualification improvement, a group of listeners is given information about ergonomics and its place in the educational system. When students are tested, the areas of spiritual and educational work are also taken into account. As a result, only 14% of the audience said that they are familiar with the concept of ergonomics and have the idea of using ergonomics, and only 9% said that they have heard about the use of ergonomics in the educational system. Such a low level of awareness of ergonomics and its place and position in the educational system allows us to assume that they are not sufficiently prepared to perform the work functions according to the professional standard of the teacher[25].

In general, most of the listeners have a low level of ergonomic culture. The results of the research showed that the training of students in the system of professional development and retraining does not provide the necessary level of the ergonomic component of the educational system for the teacher.

In conclusion, it can be said that in the process of forming an ergonomic culture, it is necessary to control the level of formation of its components such as ergonomic knowledge, skills, thinking, direction in the listeners.

If different types of control, such as tests, presentation of ergonomic knowledge and skills, are carried out during the training process, if the training activities of the trainees, gaps in knowledge are identified and eliminated in time, in our opinion, the transition the teacher's ergonomic culture improves.

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